

STUDIES IN DEHYDROGENATION. PART III.*

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In the present communication the syntheses and selenium dehydrogenation of 6:7-cyclopentenotetrahydronaphthalene and 2:2-dimethyl-6:7-cyclopentenotetrahydronaphthalene have been described. The former has been dehydrogenated to 6:7-cyclopentenonaphthalene and the latter gives 6:7-cyclopenteno-2-methylnaphthalene.

With the idea of studying the selenium dehydrogenation of hydroaromatic compounds containing a fused cyclopentane ring, 6:7-cyclopentenotetrahydronaphthalene and 2:2-dimethyl-6:7-cyclopentenotetrahydronaphthalene have been synthesised. It was found that during dehydrogenation with selenium at 300-340°, the cyclopentane ring was not affected in either case and the latter compound, which contained *gem*-dialkyl groups, a quaternary methyl group was easily eliminated when heated with selenium in a sealed tube at 320°. This result is in line with the observation of Ruzicka and Seidel (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1936, **19**, 424) that α - and β -methylhydrindenes are unaffected when heated with selenium at 350-400° but are converted into naphthalene at 450°.

For the synthesis of 6:7-cyclopentenotetrahydronaphthalene, succinic anhydride was condensed with hydrindene in nitrobenzene solution in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride when β -5-hydrindoylpropionic acid (I, R=H) was formed. The constitution of this keto-acid follows from its oxidation with alkaline permanganate to trimellitic acid. The keto-acid (I, R=H), on reduction with amalgamated zinc and hydrochloric acid, gives γ -5-hydrindylbutyric acid (II, R=H), which on cyclisation with 85% sulphuric acid gives 6:7-cyclopenteno-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (III, R=H) in 65% yield. That the cyclisation proceeds in the manner indicated, with the formation of a linear product is proved by the oxidation of the cyclic ketone (III, R=H) to 1:2:4:5-benzenetetracarboxylic acid.

(I)

(II)

(III)

This cyclic ketone on reduction by the Clemmensen method gives 6 : 7 *cyclopenteno-1 : 2 : 3 : 4*-tetrahydronaphthalene (IV, R=H), which on dehydrogenation with selenium at 300-340° yields 6 : 7-*cyclopentenonaphthalene* or 5 : 6-benzohydrindene (V, R=H).

In a similar way 2 : 2-dimethyl-6 : 7-*cyclopentenotetrahydronaphthalene* was synthesised, starting from *as*-dimethylsuccinic anhydride and hydrindene. The Friedel-Craft's reaction was carried out in nitrobenzene solution yielding mainly $\alpha\alpha$ -dimethyl- β - 5-hydrindoylpropionic acid (I, R=Me). The position of the keto group in this acid is proved by its oxidation with alkaline permanganate to trimellitic acid. The $\alpha\alpha$ -positions of the methyl groups have been assumed from analogy with the other keto-acids, synthesised previously from *as*-dimethylsuccinic anhydride and aromatic hydrocarbons. On reduction with amalgamated zinc and hydrochloric acid, the keto-acid (I, R=Me) gives $\alpha\alpha$ -dimethyl- γ -5-hydrindylbutyric acid (II, R=Me), which on cyclisation with 85% sulphuric acid gives about 85% of the theoretical yield of 1-keto-6 : 7-*cyclopenteno-2 : 2*-dimethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (III, R=Me). The structure of this linear cyclisation product is proved by its oxidation to 1 : 2 : 4 : 5-benzenetetracarboxylic acid. The cyclic ketone (III, R=Me) on reduction by Clemmensen's method gives 2 : 2-dimethyl-6 : 7-*cyclopenteno-1 : 2 : 3 : 4*-tetrahydronaphthalene (IV, R=Me). Selenium dehydrogenation of this substance was carried out in a sealed tube at 300-320° giving a good yield of 6 : 7-*cyclopenteno-2*-methylnaphthalene.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

β -5-Hydrindoylpropionic Acid (I, R=H).—To a cold solution of aluminium chloride (32 g.) in nitrobenzene (150 c.c.) a mixture of hydrindene (23 g.) and succinic anhydride (20 g.) was slowly added. The mixture was kept in the ice-bath for 6 hours and at the room temperature

for 12 hours, when it was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. Excess of nitrobenzene and hydrindene were removed in steam, the solid product dissolved in dilute sodium carbonate solution, the solution was filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The separated acid was twice crystallised from glacial acetic acid and was obtained as cubes, m. p. 122-24°. This was finally crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless cubes, m. p. 123-24°, yield 18 g. (Found: C, 71.4; H, 6.4. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 71.6; H, 6.4 per cent).

Oxidation of β -5-hydrindoylpropionic acid with alkaline potassium permanganate solution was carried by dissolving the acid (1 g.) in 100 c. c. of 5% caustic soda solution and heating with excess of permanganate solution on the steam-bath for 4 hours. The excess of permanganate was destroyed with the addition of a little alcohol and the alkaline solution filtered, acidified with hydrochloric acid and evaporated on the steam-bath. The residue was repeatedly extracted with ether and the solid residue was crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid (charcoal) in white granules, m. p. 214° with forthing, m. p. of trimellitic acid being 216°.

γ -5-Hydrindylbutyric Acid (II, R=H).—A mixture of β -5-hydrindoyl propionic acid (9 g.), amalgamated zinc (50 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c. c.) was allowed to stand for 3 hours at the ordinary temperature and then heated to boiling for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, the solvent distilled off and the oily residue extracted with sodium carbonate solution and filtered. The reduced acid separated out as an oil on acidifying the solution with hydrochloric acid, but readily solidified. This was collected and distilled, when it came over at 190-92°/6 mm. as a colourless oil which quickly solidified. It crystallised from petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°) in long needles, m. p. 56°, yield 6.2 g. (Found: C, 76.3; H, 7.9. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 76.5; H, 7.8 per cent).

6 : 7-cycloPenteno-1-keto-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (III, R=H).—A mixture of the preceding hydrindylbutyric acid (7.2 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (21.6 c. c.) and water (7.2 c. c.) was heated on the steam-bath for 1½ hours with stirring. The product was poured on ice, extracted with ether, the ether extract washed with dilute ammonia and water, dried with potassium carbonate and ether distilled off. The residual liquid distilled at 167°/6 mm. as a colourless oil, yield 4.5 g. (65% of theory). (Found: C, 83.8; H, 7.5. $C_{13}H_{14}O$ requires C, 83.9; H, 7.5 per cent).

Oxidation of 6 : 7-cycloPenteno-1-keto-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene with Alkaline Permanganate.—The cyclic ketone (1 g.) was added to

200 c.c. of 5% caustic soda solution and boiled in a brine-bath for 12 hours with excess of potassium permanganate solution. After destroying the excess of permanganate with alcohol, the alkaline solution was filtered, acidified with hydrochloric acid and evaporated. The residue was extracted with ether and on distilling off the solvent a solid product was obtained which crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid in needles, m.p. 275-76° with previous shrinking. The acid seemed to have been partially converted into the anhydride, so it was heated with acetyl chloride for 2 hours and acetic acid and acetyl chloride removed under reduced pressure. The anhydride, thus produced, was kept in a desiccator over caustic potash, m.p. 284-85° (the di-anhydride of 1 : 2 : 4 : 5-benzenetetracarboxylic acid melts at 286°).

6 : 7-cycloPenteno-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (IV, R=H).—The foregoing ketone (4.8 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (25 g.) and hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, washed, dried, ether removed and the residue distilled over sodium as a thin colourless liquid, b.p. 125-26°/6 mm., yield 3.1 g. (Found : C, 90.8 ; H, 9.2. $C_{13}H_{16}$ requires C, 90.7 ; H, 9.3 per cent).

Selenium Dehydrogenation of 6 : 7-cycloPenteno-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene to 5 : 6-Benzohydrindene.—The hydrocarbon (3 g.) was heated with powdered selenium (5 g.) at 300-310° for 8 hours and at 320-345° for 16 hours in a metal-bath. Part of the dehydrogenated product sublimed into the neck of the flask. The product was thoroughly extracted with ether, the solvent evaporated and the slightly coloured crystalline residue distilled over sodium under reduced pressure as a colourless solid crystallising from alcohol in flakes, m.p. 94°. (Found : C, 92.7 ; H, 7.2. $C_{13}H_{12}$ requires C, 92.2 ; H, 7.1 per cent). The *picrate* was prepared in alcoholic solution and it crystallised from alcohol in golden yellow needles, m.p. 120-21°. (Found : C, 57.3 ; H, 3.8. $C_{19}H_{15}O_7N_3$ requires C, 57.4 ; H, 3.8 per cent).

αα-Dimethyl-β-5-hydrindoylpropionic Acid (I, R=Me) was prepared from *αα*-dimethylsuccinic anhydride (38.4 g.), hydrindene (36 g.) and aluminium chloride (52 g.) in nitrobenzene (150 c.c.) exactly as in the case of *β*-4-hydrindoylpropionic acid. The crude product was crystallised from acetic acid and the first crop recrystallised from alcohol (charcoal) as colourless prisms, m.p. 139-40°, yield 15 g. No sharp melting substance could be isolated from the acetic acid mother-liquor. (Found : C, 73.1 ; H, 7.3. $C_{15}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 73.2 ; H, 7.3 per cent).

The *methyl ester* was obtained by the action of methyl alcoholic hydrochloride as a colourless thick liquid, b.p. 190-91°/6 mm. (Found : C, 73.6 ; H, 7.8. $C_{14}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.8 ; H, 7.7 per cent).

Oxidation of $\alpha\alpha$ -dimethyl- β -5-hydrindoylpropionic acid with alkaline permanganate was carried out exactly as in the case of β -5-hydrindoylpropionic acid and trimellitic acid (m.p. 214°) was isolated.

$\alpha\alpha$ -Dimethyl- γ -5-hydrindylbutyric Acid (II, R = Me).— $\alpha\alpha$ -Dimethyl- β -5-hydrindoylpropionic acid (8 g.) was reduced with amalgamated zinc (40 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.) exactly as in the preparation of γ -5-hydrindylbutyric acid. The reduced solid was purified by extraction with sodium carbonate solution. It crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in colourless needles, m.p. 82-83°. (Found : C, 77.5 ; H, 8.6. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 77.6 ; H, 8.6 per cent).

6 : 7-cyclopenteno-1-keto-2 : 2-dimethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (III, R = Me).—The foregoing hydrindylbutyric acid (7 g.) was cyclised by heating with sulphuric acid (21 c.c.) and water (7 c.c.). The product was obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. 170°/10 mm., yield 5.4 g. (85% of theory). (Found : C, 83.8 ; H, 8.5. $C_{15}H_{18}O$ requires C, 84.1 ; H, 8.4 per cent).

Oxidation of the foregoing keto-cyclic compound (III, R = Me) to benzene-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetracarboxylic acid was carried out exactly in the manner described for the oxidation of 6 : 7-cyclopenteno-1-keto-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene. The anhydride of the product melted at 284°.

6 : 7-cyclopenteno-2-2-dimethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene (IV, R = Me).—The preceding cyclic ketone (III, R = Me) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (15 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, the ether extract washed with water, dried and ether distilled off, when 1.7 g. of solid residue were obtained which crystallised from petrol ether (b.p. 40-60°) in minute prisms, m.p. 82°. (Found : C, 89.8 ; H, 10.1. $C_{15}H_{20}$ requires C, 90.0 ; H, 10.0 per cent).

Dehydrogenation of 6 : 7-cyclopenteno-2 : 2-dimethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—A mixture of the hydrocarbon (1 g.) and selenium (1.5 g.) was heated in a sealed tube at 300-320° for 24 hours. The product was thoroughly extracted with ether which left a slightly coloured solid on evaporation. This distilled over sodium under reduced pressure as a colourless solid (0.6 g.). The hydrocarbon, thus obtained, on being washed with a concentrated alcoholic solution of picric acid (0.6 g.) gave a picrate which

after recrystallisation melted at 107-108°. (Found : C, 58.2 ; H, 4.2. $C_{20}H_{17}O_7N_3$ requires C, 58.4 ; H, 4.1 per cent). The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the picrate by distribution between ammonia and ether. The ether solution was washed with water and the solvent evaporated. The hydrocarbon, thus obtained, crystallised from methyl alcohol in beautiful shining flakes, m.p. 104°. (Found : C, 92.3 ; H, 7.7. $C_{14}H_{14}$ requires C, 92.3 ; H, 7.7 per cent).

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